

Skills
4 eosoc

Supporting | eosoc

Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
UK Research
and Innovation

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
- Commons

www.skills4eosoc.eu

Skills4EOSC Training Courses

2025

Introduction

Skills4EOSC offers a comprehensive **training program** designed to equip researchers, data stewards, and other stakeholders with essential skills for navigating the evolving landscape of **Open Science** and the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**.

Skills4EOSC follows a Train-the-Trainer approach, empowering trainers from Competence Centres, research organisations, and communities. Trainers who complete the programme and demonstrate the required competencies receive certification, ensuring high-quality and consistent training delivery. **They are officially recognised as Master Trainers.**

BY PARTICIPATING IN OUR COURSES, YOU'LL GAIN:

- Capability to support evidence-informed decision-making through Open Science
- Insights into developing and implementing Open Science policies
- Awareness of the role of Open Science in addressing global challenges and future research
- Practical skills in Open Science practices and their implementation
- Knowledge of FAIR principles and their application in various research contexts
- Strategies for effective research data management and governance
- Understanding of Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) in Open Science
- Skills for creating and nurturing Data Steward communities and networks
- Techniques for fostering collaboration among diverse Open Science stakeholders

COURSE AREA	TITLE OF THE COURSE	WHERE
GENERAL	IMPLEMENTING FAIR-BY-DESIGN METHODOLOGY	<u>COURSE</u>
	YAICOS (YET ANOTHER INTRODUCTORY COURSE ON OPEN SCIENCE)	Available from August 2025
SCIENCE4POLICY	OPEN SCIENCE IS THE NEW NORM	Available from August 2025
	ELSI AND DATA GOVERNANCE	
	INTRODUCTION TO EVIDENCE-INFORMED DECISION-MAKING	
	OPEN SCIENCE STAKEHOLDERS AND COLLABORATION STRATEGIES	
	EMPOWERING THE FUTURE OF RESEARCH WITH OPEN SCIENCE	
	OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES SUPPORT OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES	
	IMPLEMENTING OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES	
OPEN SCIENCE READY INSTITUTIONS	OPEN LICENCES FOR DATA SOFTWARE AND CODE	<u>1st ROUND / 2nd ROUND</u>
	LEARNING PATH FOR ELSI PROFESSIONALS: ELSI PERSPECTIVES IN OPEN SCIENCE	<u>1st ROUND / 2nd ROUND</u>
	LEARNING PATH FOR (DATA) LIBRARIANS: TECHNICAL SKILLS ARE THE BRIDGE TO REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH	<u>COURSE</u>
	TEACHING OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT FOR UNDERGRADUATES	<u>COURSE</u>
	SHAPING OPEN SCIENCE CHAMPIONS: A TRAIN-THE-TRAINERS COURSE FOR EDUCATORS OF PHD CANDIDATES	Available from August 2025
THEMATIC OPEN SCIENCE	SSH RESEARCHERS AND OS	Available from August 2025
	THE RESEARCH COMMUNITY IN SOLID EARTH SCIENCES	
	OPEN SCIENCE FOR EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS IN CLIMATE CHANGE	
	OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS FOR DIGITAL COLLECTIONS CURATORS	
	DATA MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (RI) PROFESSIONALS	

IMPLEMENTING FAIR-BY-DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Description	This course focuses on the practical application of the FAIR-by-Design methodology developed by Skills4EOSC. Participants will learn how to design and implement FAIR data practices in their projects.			Who should attend	Master Trainers, project managers, data stewards, and researchers involved in project design.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=19

YAICOS (YET ANOTHER INTRODUCTORY COURSE ON OPEN SCIENCE)

Description	YAICOS is Yet Another Introductory Course on Open Science: a self-paced course designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the foundations, benefits, challenges, and practical applications of Open Science (OS). Through engaging video lectures, curated resources, and self-assessment formative quizzes, learners will explore how Open Science principles are reshaping research culture across disciplines and fostering responsible, transparent, and collaborative research.			Who should attend	Anybody interested in "Open Science" (including, researchers at any stage of their career, doctoral students, research support staff, librarians, and educators) who are new to Open Science or seeking to strengthen their foundational knowledge. It may also benefit policymakers, scientific journalist and other stakeholders in the research ecosystem.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	Available from August 2025

OPEN SCIENCE FOR EVIDENCE-INFORMED DECISION MAKING AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION					
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Who should attend	Master trainers, Policy Actors (Decision Makers, Civil Servants, Honest Brokers).
<p>Registration and access to the self-paced material will be available 10 days prior to the course. It is important to have studied the material before the participation in the live course. Each course provides a specialised badge. Complete all 7 courses of this learning path to receive the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making Instructor” certification.</p>					
Course 1	Open Science is the new norm				
Description	This course introduces the paradigm shift towards open science, exploring its fundamental principles and impact on society. It delves into accountability and transparency and contrasts open science practices with traditional closed science models. Participants will gain a foundational understanding of how open science promotes collaboration and innovation and the basic concepts and societal implications of open science.				
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025				
Course 2	ELSI and Data Governance				
Description	This course will cover the legal and ethical frameworks and considerations for implementing OS practices. Additionally, participants will examine the challenges and opportunities for Open Science within the EU regulatory framework, focusing on data governance and legislative strategies for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research.				
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025				
Course 3	Introduction to Evidence-informed Decision-Making				
Description	This course bridges the gap between open science and the practice of evidence-informed decision-making. It delves into the role of policy, the integration of evidence in decision-making processes, and the stakeholders involved. Participants will learn about open science outputs and tools that support decision-making, and how to interpret statistical data to derive actionable insights.				
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025				

Course 4	Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies
Description	This course focuses on identifying and engaging with the diverse stakeholders involved in open science. It explores effective collaboration strategies to foster partnerships among researchers, institutions, policymakers, and the public. Participants will learn how to navigate the complex landscape of open science collaborations to maximise research impact and innovation.
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025
Course 5	Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science
Description	This course explores how open science can shape the future of research and decision-making, emphasising investment, capacity building, and integrating advanced technologies like AI. Participants will learn the importance of investing in open science, developing training programs, and leveraging AI to enhance research practices and support evidence-informed decision-making.
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025
Course 6	Open Science policies support Open Science practices
Description	This course explores how open science policies underpin and facilitate the adoption of open science practices. It examines the roles of stakeholders, the challenges and barriers to implementation, and the cultural shifts necessary for successful adoption. Participants will also learn about responsible research assessment and review successful case studies of open science policy implementation.
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025
Course 7	Implementing Open Science policies
Description	This course delves into the practical aspects of developing and implementing open science policies. It covers profiles of key policymakers, essential elements for effective policy development, the integration of open science workflows, and strategies for monitoring and evaluating the impact of these policies.
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025

OPEN LICENCES FOR DATA SOFTWARE AND CODE

Description	This 2-hour training unit equips trainers with essential skills to teach research output licensing. It covers adapting content to local contexts, applying for licences throughout projects, complying with funder and institutional requirements, and aligning with research discipline and project aims.			Who should attend	Data Stewards and data professionals with basic knowledge of rights to research output.
Level	Intermediate	Type	Async	Learning Platform	<p>1st Round https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=29</p> <p>2nd Round https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=59#section-4</p>

LEARNING PATH FOR ELSI PROFESSIONALS: ELSI PERSPECTIVES IN OPEN SCIENCE

Description	This course introduces legal drivers and motivations behind key regulations like the AI Act and GDPR. Through practical discussions and case studies, it connects legal aspects to researchers' commitments to FAIR principles, reproducibility, and Open Science goals. It examines the implications of laws on research from both ELSI and researcher perspectives, addressing potential frictions and opportunities created by regulations like the AI Act.			Who should attend	ELSI professionals and researchers.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	<p>1st Round https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=48</p> <p>2nd Round https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=58</p>

LEARNING PATH FOR (DATA) LIBRARIANS: TECHNICAL SKILLS ARE THE BRIDGE TO REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH

Description	This course focuses on technical skills as key enablers of reproducible research. It covers the distinction between reproducibility and replicability, emphasising the crucial role of technical aspects in achieving reproducibility. It explores the importance of responsible research conduct and Open Science principles concerning reproducibility. Participants will reflect on the data librarian’s role in supporting reproducible research, considering various disciplinary requirements, issues, and tools. It also provides insights into technological solutions such as programming and data wrangling.			Who should attend	Data librarians and data curators.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=47

TEACHING OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT FOR UNDERGRADUATES

Description	This course is designed to prepare trainers for delivering the online course Introduction to Open Science and Research Data Management to undergraduate students. Trainers will explore the six course modules: Introduction to Open Science, Open Access, Copyright and Licensing, Introduction to Research Data Management, Research Data Management in Practice, and Research Impact and Visibility. By completing the course, trainers will become familiar with both the course content and practicalities.			Who should attend	Educators and trainers responsible for teaching undergraduate university students.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=68

SHAPING OPEN SCIENCE CHAMPIONS: A TRAIN-THE-TRAINERS COURSE FOR EDUCATORS OF PHD CANDIDATES

Description	This course invites educators to become mentors guiding PhD candidates towards a more open, transparent, and collaborative research landscape, giving them “a ticket 2 Open Science”. Participants will navigate key Open Science stations, including open access publishing, FAIR data principles, research data management, and responsible research and innovation (RRI). Throughout this journey, trainers will not only gain foundational knowledge but also acquire practical teaching strategies to engage doctoral students as future Open Science champions.			Who should attend	PhD mentors, Mid-senior career researchers, and/or academic staff responsible for delivering Open Science training to doctoral students.
Level	Beginner	Type	Async	Learning Platform	Available from August 2025

SSH RESEARCHERS AND OS			
Description	<p>The course targets SSH scholars working as active researchers at any career stage, and staff like librarians, editors or research infrastructure professionals supporting the SSH research community. SSH is characterised by a diversity of sub-disciplines and there are distinct challenges in how to manage complex topics such as data management, ethics, and publications. This training will focus specifically on the issues faced by SSH scholars and try to provide a platform and ideas for all participants to confidently deliver training in their own context.</p>	Who should attend	<p>Researchers in the Social Sciences and Humanities.</p>
Level	Beginner / Intermediate	Type	Async
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025		

THE RESEARCH COMMUNITY IN SOLID EARTH SCIENCES			
Description	<p>The program is structured to demonstrate how Open Science and FAIR principles are concretely implemented in the EPOS (European Plate Observing System) portal. Through practical examples and case studies, participants will gain essential skills to understand the importance of Open Science in the context of Earth Sciences, apply FAIR principles in geoscientific data management, effectively use the EPOS portal for research and data sharing, and integrate Open Science practices into their research work.</p>	Who should attend	<p>Researchers, PhD students, teachers.</p>
Level	Beginner / Intermediate	Type	Async
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025		

OPEN SCIENCE FOR EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS IN CLIMATE CHANGE

Description	Participants will learn about data lifecycle, research data management, Open Science and FAIR principles, and data management planning. The course introduces major climate science infrastructural initiatives and emphasises the importance of understanding Open Science policies and practices in the climate change domain. It aims to equip junior researchers with the skills needed to conduct transparent, collaborative, and impactful climate research.	Who should attend	Researchers in Climate Change.
Level	Beginner / Intermediate	Type	Async
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025		

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS FOR DIGITAL COLLECTIONS CURATORS

Description	This course teaches curators and scientists how to digitise object-based collections and make them openly accessible. Participants learn to apply FAIR principles, use standardised metadata, and create sustainable digital repositories. The training covers from digitisation techniques and data visualisation, emphasising the transformation of physical artefacts into “Open Collections”, to ethical and legal aspects of managing digital open collections. This course aims to enhance the accessibility and value of scientific collections for global research, bridging the gap between traditional curatorial practices and modern digital accessibility standards.	Who should attend	Curators and scientists in Libraries, Archives and Museums (LAMs), universities and research infrastructures working with object-based digital collections.
Level	Beginner / Intermediate	Type	Async
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025		

DATA MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (RI) PROFESSIONALS			
Description	The course provides a comprehensive overview of the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy in Research Infrastructures. It covers topics such as the role of data policy, data typologies, metadata, operational considerations for managers, data lifecycle, workflows, user groups, open data, data sharing and access restrictions, certification mechanisms, and FAIR principles.		Who should attend
Level	Beginner	Type	Async
Learning Platform	Available from August 2025		

www.skills4eosc.eu

in X zenodo

Supporting eosc

 Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
 UK Research
and Innovation

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].